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for exercising in boys and girls were not obtained. The results are consistent with the literature and show that girls are more prone to emotional and uncontrolled eating compared to boys, who more often turn to other coping strategies such as alcohol consumption or gambling to overcome negative emotions. According to our results, working with adolescents with PH symptoms requires a different approach for girls and boys, but also needs considering cognitive and behavioral eating and weight control strategies that are important in the maintenance of ED symptoms.

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Keywords: eating disorder symptoms, exercise motives, eating patterns, body mass index, adolescents

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Razrešenje dijagnoze i reagovanje na averzivne emocije deteta kod majki dece sa cerebralnom paralizom

Razrešenje dijagnoze podrazumeva roditeljski odnos prema detetovoj dijagnozi, odnosno kognitivno i emotivno prihvatanje detetovog zdravstvenog stanja i posledica koje ono sa sobom nosi. Koncept razrešenja svoj teorijski oslonac nalazi u Teoriji afektivne vezanosti i iz nje proisteklim istraživanjima. Ona su konzistentno potvrdila da odsustvo razrešenja ometa roditeljske kapacitete da prepoznaju i senzitivno odgovore na emocionalne signale svog deteta. Sprovedeno je istraživanje sa ciljem ispitivanja relacija između majčinog razrešenja u odnosu na detetovu dijagnozu cerebralne paralize (razrešen/ nerazrešen) i njene sposobnosti da u vremeni i adekvatno odreaguje na averzivne emocije svog deteta. Pošli smo od pretpostavke da postoji razlika između razrešenih i nerazrešenih majki u odnosu na reagovanje na averzivne emocije deteta, pri čemu se očekuje da će majke sa nerazrešenim odnosom imati veće poteškoće da senzitivno reaguju na averzivne emocije svog deteta. U svrhu procene odnosa prema dijagnozi sa majkama je obavljen polustruktuisani Intervju o reagovanju na dijagnozu (Pianta & Marvin, 1992). Svi intervjui su snimani, nakon čega su dobijeni odgovori kodirani koristeći Klasifikacioni sistem o reagovanju na dijagnozu (Pianta & Marvin, 1993). Skala roditeljskih reakcija na averzivne emocije deteta (Fabes, Eisenberg, & Bernzweig,

1990) je primenjena za procenu reagovanja majki na averzivne emocije deteta. Uzorak je činilo 100 majki dece sa cerebralnom paralizom, uzrasta od 2 do 7 godina. Rezultati su pokazali da nisu dobijene statistički značajne razlike u načinima reagovanja na ispoljavanje detetovih averzivnih emocije, s obzirom na majčin status razrešenja $F(6,93)=1.19$, $p=.32$. Preciznije, majke su, bez obzira na status razrešenja, najčešće dominantno koristile podržavajuće strategije u reagovanju, odnosno na problem i na emocije usmerene reakcije, kao i podsticanje izražavanja emocija. Najređe korištena strategija se pokazala strategija kažnjavanja. To su ohrabrujući podaci s obzirom da deca sa cerebralnom paralizom, kao i sa drugim vidovima zdravstvenih, a posebno neuroloških stanja, mogu imati teškoće u ispoljavanju emotivnih doživljaja, što posledično može da oteža adekatno prepoznavanje detetovih emocionalnih reagovanja. Njihovim roditeljima je teže da ispravno protumače detetovo ispoljavanje besa, tuge, straha ili neke druge averzivne emocije. Postoji i mogućnost da deca koja su od ranog uzrasta izložena stresogenim dijagnostičkim i terapijskim procedurama, koje zahtevaju regulaciju negativnog afekta, bolje tolerišu averzivne emocije. Važno je naglasiti značaj roditeljskog razrešenja za senzitivno prepoznavanje detetovih potreba i majčinog podržavajućeg reagovanja u situacijama ispoljavanja averzivnih emocija kod dece sa hroničnim zdravstvenim stanjima.

Ključne reči: majčino razrešenje, averzivne emocije, deca

Maternal resolution of diagnosis and coping with negative emotions of children with cerebral palsy

Resolution of diagnosis implies the parental attitude towards their child's diagnosis, i.e. cognitive and emotional acceptance of the child's health condition and its implications. The concept of resolution is grounded in the attachment theory and studies based on it. These studies have consistently found that the lack of resolution hinders parental capacity to recognize and sensitively respond to emotional cues from the child. We conducted a study aimed at investigating the relationship between maternal resolution with respect to the child's diagnosis of cerebral palsy (resolved/unresolved) and their capabilities to respond in a timely and adequate fashion to their child's aversive emotions. We hypothesized that there is a difference in reacting to their child's aversive emotions between mothers who are resolved vs. those unresolved and we expected those that are unresolved to have more difficulties in reacting sensitively to their child's aversive emotions. In order to assess resolution of diagnosis semi-structured Reaction to Diagnosis Interviews (Pianta & Marvin, 1992) were held with mothers. All interviews were recorded and the answers were coded using the Reaction to Diagnosis Classification System (Pianta & Marvin, 1993). The Coping with Children's Negative Emotion Scale (Fabes, Eisenberg,

& Bernzweig, 1990) was used to assess maternal reactions to their children's negative emotions. Our sample included 100 mothers of children with cerebral palsy, aged 2 to 7 years. Our results yielded no statistically significant differences in ways of reacting to manifestations of children's aversive emotions with regard to maternal resolution status $F(6,93)=1.19$, $p=.32$. More precisely, regardless of their resolution status, mothers predominantly used supportive strategies, i.e. strategies focused on the problem and emotionally focused strategies, along with strategies that encourage expressing emotions. The least used strategy was punishment. This is encouraging since children with cerebral palsy and other types of health conditions, particularly neurological, can have difficulties in expressing emotions which makes it harder to recognize their emotional reactions. Parents are faced with difficulties in accurately interpreting manifestations of anger, sadness, fear or any other aversive emotion. It is also conceivable that children subjected from a young age to stressful diagnostic and therapeutic procedures that require regulating negative affect, subsequently tolerate aversive emotions better. It is important to underline the importance of parental resolution for sensitively recognizing and reacting supportively in situations when children with chronic health conditions exhibit aversive emotions.

Keywords: maternal resolution, aversive emotions, children

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The role of past physician-patient communication in passivity normalization during childbirth

One of the most important determinants of patients' adherence to the treatment is the quality of the physician-patient relationship. Studies show that overall positive communication with healthcare workers positively affects treatment adherence and the other desirable patients' behaviors. Therefore, positive experiences of physician-patient interaction increase the frequency of normative behaviors. In this